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Codes

All over the world that are different varieties of languages the people might know how to speak or might not. There are people who only speak one language which are monolingual there are people who speak two languages which are bilingual and that are people who can speak more than two language to retire multi-lingual. However, people are required to use or to select one particular code or language when they are speaking they can use only one code or they can switch from one code to the other and that depends on the person that they are talking with or the situation.

Besides, this code switching can happen like in very short sentences like one sentence for example can be in the Spanish and then the other sentence can be in English and it is cold code switching. One example of a country which uses code switching is Singapore in this country they have the ability to shift from one language to another and it is very accepted and it's seem as a normal activity in this country they have four official languages English, the Mandarin variety off Chinese, Camille, and Malay, which all of them are the national language

There are certain concerns around and multilingual Society we must identify in which one speaker goes from language A to language B, basically the question is when they decide which language to use. According to the reading what brings the speaker to choose variety X of a language rather than a variety Y or even language A rather than language B. can be sometimes the solidarity, accommodation to listeners, choice of topic, and perceived social and cultural distance.

Furthermore, one of the characteristics that have a big impact on the language decision that the speaker is using is the solidarity. In fact, multilingual people know that they are not going to speak with a person in German if the person does not speak German. Empathic communication, if the speaker knows English and the other speaker knows English too, that is the best and quickest decision they can make in order to have a communication. in other words motivation of the speaker is a very important consideration in the choice, Although not all the time motivation is conscious if the speaker listened to a person using

French and the speaker knows how to speak French, for sure the speaker will switch into the language code that the other person is using and this is an automatically performance, and this is how code switching works.

In the other hand, the diglossia speakers are quite aware of what is going on; thus, they know that they are changing from one language to the other and vice versa. As a matter of fact when speakers have the ability to communicate in different languages, they also change their behaviors, some languages can be easy or difficult for them depending on the how the communication is held, nevertheless the way the speaker shares his or her ideas it can express power, solidarity, or identity which create diversity on people; in general we must say that code switching can be a very useful social skill for every person in the world.

References:

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